

Unwashed *Aspergillus niger* spores germinate spontaneously: challenging standard lab protocols

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Abstract

Aspergillus niger spore germination is a critical process in fields ranging from food spoilage and human health to biotechnology. Standard laboratory protocols investigating germination typically rely on washed spores, primarily to remove known density-dependent self-inhibitors. This research challenges the assumptions underlying these protocols by demonstrating markedly different germination dynamics between washed conidia and unwashed conidia harvested with minimal physical contact. Our preliminary data reveal that unwashed *A. niger* spores germinate readily under minimal nutrient conditions, whereas washed spores remain dormant. We hypothesize that unwashed spores possess and/or rapidly release endogenous molecular triggers upon hydration—a "starter pack" sufficient for germination initiation, often removed during washing. Initial analysis of spore-conditioned water supports this hypothesis. This report outlines preliminary findings and proposes further investigation using mass spectrometry and biochemical analyses to elucidate the chemical nature of these endogenous factors, ultimately aiming to understand fungal spore germination in the natural world.

Introduction

Aspergillus niger is a ubiquitous fungus with significant dual impacts—acting as a major food spoilage organism and opportunistic pathogen, while also serving as a cell factory in industrial biotechnology for enzyme and acid production (Dijksterhuis, 2017;

Wösten, 2019). The transition from a dormant asexual spore (conidium) to active hyphal growth via germination is the critical first step initiating both detrimental colonization and beneficial fermentation processes. Consequently, understanding the mechanisms that trigger and regulate spore germination is of fundamental biological importance and holds immense practical value.

Aspergillus germination research has investigated environmental factors like temperature and water availability (Marin et al., 1998) and nutrient stimuli, such as specific sugars and amino acids (Hayer et al., 2013, 2014; Ijadpanahsaravi et al., 2021, 2022). A common practice involves the extensive washing of spores prior to experimentation. This step is typically justified by the need to remove known germination self-inhibitors, such as C8 oxylipins (e.g., 1-octen-3-ol), which accumulate at high spore densities and prevent premature germination on the parent colony (Chitarra et al., 2004; Herrero-Garcia et al., 2011). This washing aims to create a "clean slate," ensuring germination depends solely on added external triggers.

However, this standard approach potentially overlooks the spore's intrinsic capabilities and natural context. My preliminary investigations present a direct challenge to this paradigm. Using *A. niger* conidia harvested by tapping (a method minimizing physical manipulation and contact with culture medium), we observed significant germination initiation (swelling and germ tube emergence) in conditions essentially devoid of external nutrients, where identically treated but thoroughly washed spores remained dormant. This striking difference suggests that the standard washing procedure may remove not only inhibitors but also endogenous inducers of germination.

Based on these initial findings, I propose the hypothesis that *A. niger* conidia possess an inherent "starter pack" of molecules—either loosely associated with the surface, embedded within the outer wall layers, or rapidly released from internal stores

upon hydration—that are sufficient to trigger the initial stages of germination without requiring significant external nutrient input. The observation that spore-conditioned water (SCW), prepared by briefly hydrating tapped spores, can induce germination in washed spores further supports this hypothesis.

What might constitute this "starter pack"? The complex biochemistry of the *Aspergillus* conidium offers several candidates. Known stored compatible solutes like trehalose and mannitol could leak. The spore wall itself, rich in polysaccharides (glucans, mannans, chitin) and proteins (small peptides, surface proteins), could release soluble fragments or signalling molecules upon hydration (Blango et al., 2019; Horikoshi & Iida, 1964; Pinzan et al., 2024). Indeed, phosphate compounds are known to be released from *A. niger* upon water contact (Damle & Krishnan, 1956). Furthermore, spores contain pre-packaged mRNA and enzymes, including cell wall remodeling enzymes, ready for rapid deployment (Osherov & May, 2001; Van Leeuwen et al., 2013). It is likely a combination of these factors, released into the immediate microenvironment upon encountering water, that drives the self-sufficient germination observed in unwashed spores. Washing spores can hinder germination, potentially by removing essential nutrients. For example, while *Sclerotinia fructicola* spores harvested by brushing or flooding achieved 85.5% germination, their germ tube production significantly decreased after extensive washing and centrifugation (Gottlieb, 1950). Conversely, studies suggesting unwashed spores germinate attribute this not to inherent spore leachates but likely to contamination from nutrient-rich culture media, especially sugars.

Elucidating the nature of these endogenous triggers carries significant implications. Fundamentally, it promises a more ecologically relevant understanding of how *Aspergillus* spores initiate colonization in natural environments, which often lack the high nutrient concentrations typical of laboratory media. Methodologically, it calls into

question the interpretation of germination studies relying exclusively on washed spores, potentially highlighting experimental artifacts. Practically, identifying the components of this "starter pack" could unveil novel targets for controlling unwanted fungal growth in low-nutrient settings crucial for food preservation and preventing infections. Conversely, understanding these self-triggering mechanisms could inform strategies for optimizing spore handling and germination efficiency in biotechnological applications. This research aims to chemically characterize these endogenous factors and redefine our understanding of the minimal requirements for *Aspergillus* germination.

Materials and Methods

Aspergillus niger N402 (Bos et al., 1988) was the primary species used. Additional species, including *Aspergillus clavatus* NRRL1 (Arnaud et al., 2012), *Aspergillus nidulans* FGSC A4 (Arnaud et al., 2012), *Aspergillus oryzae* RIB40 (Machida et al., 2005), and *Aspergillus terreus* NHI 2624 (Arnaud et al., 2012), were also used for comparative experiments. Strains were typically cultured on minimal medium (MM) with 1% glucose and 1.5% agar as described (Ijadpanahsaravi et al., 2021). To control for potential carry-over effects from glucose-rich media, spores were also grown on MM agar plates supplemented with arginine 1% instead of glucose, as arginine is a weak germination trigger for *A. niger*. Plates were incubated at 30°C for more than 7 days to allow for sporulation.

To minimize contact with the culture medium and obtain "unwashed" spores, conidia were harvested by carefully inverting the sporulating agar plate and gently tapping the bottom. Released conidia were collected directly from the inverted plate lid using a sterile, moist cotton swab and immediately suspended in sterile pure water (typically 1 ml).

Washed spores were prepared using a standard laboratory protocol. Briefly, spores harvested with a cotton swab wetted with water from colonies are placed into sterile water. The suspension was subjected to 2 cycles of centrifugation at 4000 g for 5 min and resuspension in iced-fresh sterile water to remove residual medium components and potential self-inhibitors.

Spore-Conditioned Water (SCW) was prepared from suspensions of unwashed spores. Time-course SCW was generated by incubating aliquots of the initial spore suspension at 30°C for different durations, followed by filtration (Millipore, 0.2 µm). T₀ SCW was filtered immediately after spore collection. T₁ to T₅ SCW were incubated for 1 to 5 hours, respectively, before filtration. T₂₄ supernatant was incubated for 24 hours before filtration. To evaluate heat-labile components (e.g., proteins, peptides), a portion of filtered T₀ SCW was heat-treated at 100°C for 8 minutes.

Germination assays were conducted in 96-well plates using washed *A. niger* spores resuspended in various media: SCW preparations (T₀-T₅, heat-treated T₀, cross-species SCW), a synthetic mimic solution, or water (negative control). Unwashed spores suspended directly in water were used for comparison in some experiments. Spore germination was monitored using an oCelloScope system (Biosense Solutions) for 24 h at 30 °C. Live imaging data analysis from SCW treatments was challenging due to object instability, likely caused by uncharacterized SCW compounds. Consequently, germination percentage was evaluated from images captured at specific time points (e.g., 15 h, 24 h).

TLC was initially attempted for SCW component analysis but proved unsuitable, likely due to low analyte concentrations. HPLC analysis of filtered T₀ SCW identified and quantified soluble sugars and polyols. Detected compounds included trehalose, glucose, fructose, mannitol, arabinose, glycerol, ribose, rhamnose, N-acetylglucosamine, mannose, and xylose, with some present at low or inconsistent levels. A synthetic mimic of T₀ SCW,

based on HPLC quantification, was prepared in pure water with the following approximate concentrations: trehalose (0.05 mM), glucose (4.6 mM), fructose (0.21 mM), mannitol (0.73 mM), arabinose (0.05 mM), and glycerol (0.18 mM). This solution was then tested for its ability to induce *A. niger* spore germination.

Preliminary Findings

Our investigation into *Aspergillus niger* germination revealed that endogenous factors, typically removed by washing, play a critical role. Unwashed spores germinated readily in water, unlike washed spores, which remained dormant (Figure 1B comparison). Spore-conditioned water (SCW) from unwashed spores induced robust germination in washed spores (Figure 1A vs 1B), indicating release of germination-promoting factors.

The germination induced by T₀ SCW in washed *A. niger* spores was comparable in efficiency to that induced by the strong amino acid trigger proline (10 mM) when combined with the surfactant Tween 80 (1%) (Figures 1A, 2C). Notably, this suggests SCW contains highly effective germination cues. In fact, T₀ SCW induced germination more efficiently than 10 mM proline, achieving levels comparable to the synergistic effect observed with 10 mM proline combined with 1% Tween 80 (Figures 1A, 2A, and 2C).

The phenomenon of enhanced germination in unwashed versus washed spores was not limited to *A. niger*. Unwashed conidia of *A. clavatus*, *A. oryzae*, *A. terreus*, and *A. nidulans* also showed qualitatively higher germination percentages compared to their washed counterparts when incubated in the presence of alanine (Figure 3).

Interestingly, SCW prepared from unwashed spores of other *Aspergillus* species (*A. terreus*, *A. oryzae*, *A. nidulans*, *A. clavatus*) appeared to stimulate the germination of washed *A. niger* spores even more effectively than SCW prepared from *A. niger* itself. This contrasts with previous findings showing density-dependent inhibition by conspecific

spores (Ijadpanahsaravi et al., 2024) and suggests complex inter-species chemical communication during germination initiation.

The germination-inducing capacity of SCW diminished as the incubation time of the conditioning spores increased. T₀ SCW (filtered immediately) was most potent, while T₅ SCW (filtered after 5 hours of incubation) was largely ineffective. This suggests either the consumption of released triggers by the conditioning spores or the subsequent release of inhibitory compounds during prolonged incubation.

HPLC analysis of T₀ SCW confirmed the presence of several sugars and polyols, including trehalose, glucose, fructose, mannitol, arabinose, and glycerol, albeit at relatively low millimolar concentrations (Figure 4). A synthetic mimic solution containing these identified compounds at their measured concentrations induced germination in washed spores more effectively than high concentrations of glucose (50 mM) or proline (10 mM), indicating synergistic effects. However, the synthetic mimic was less effective and induced germination more slowly (7-8 hours) than native T₀ SCW (4-5 hours). This suggests the presence of additional, unidentified bioactive components (e.g., other sugars, amino acids, peptides, fatty acids, ions, volatiles) contributing to the full potency of SCW.

SCW was observed to be more effective at inducing germination in washed spores compared to unwashed spores. This counter-intuitive result implies that unwashed spores may retain not only the "starter pack" of promoters but also some level of inhibitory factors, which are removed from washed spores, making them more responsive to the externally supplied promoters in SCW.

While SCW effectively triggers germination, spores germinating in SCW were observed to initiate conidiophore formation (asexual reproduction) after 24 hours, suggesting the nutrient-poor conditions are sufficient for initiating germination but not for sustained vegetative growth.

Proposed Future Analysis

Given the limitations of targeted analyses (TLC, HPLC) and the observation that the synthetic mimic did not fully replicate the potency of native SCW, a more comprehensive approach is warranted. Untargeted metabolomics (e.g., using LC-MS and/or GC-MS) is proposed as a superior method to identify the full spectrum of small molecules (including amino acids, organic acids, fatty acids, peptides, and other potential triggers or inhibitors) present in SCW derived from unwashed spores under different conditions (e.g., T₀ vs. T₅).

Figure 1. Washed *Aspergillus niger* spores after 10 hours of incubation at 30°C, in T₀ spore-conditioned water (SCW) (A) and water (B).

Figure 2. Washed *Aspergillus niger* spores after 10-hour incubation at 30°C in: (A) 10 mM proline, (B) 10 mM Tween 80, and (C) 10 mM proline + 1% Tween 80.

Figure 3. Washed and unwashed conidia of *Aspergillus niger* (A-B), *A. clavatus* (C-D), *A. oryzae* (E-F), *A. terreus* (G-H), and *A. nidulans* (I-J) were incubated at 30°C and exposed to alanine after 24 hours.

Figure 4. HPLC chromatograms of T₀ spore-conditioned water (SCW) derived from unwashed *Aspergillus niger* conidia. Peaks eluting at retention times corresponding to authentic standards for glucose (approx. 9.2 min), mannitol (approx. 10.2 min), and trehalose (approx. 7.6 min) are indicated.

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